

Science Workshop Practice in Nigerian Secondary Schools: Its Limitations and Needed Reforms

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to examine the benefits of science workshop practice in science and technology education in Nigerian secondary schools. It also identifies the factors responsible for its limited or poor usage and make some useful recommendations on the way forward. Science and technology education (though initiated from the primary school) actually has its root in the secondary school and cannot be achieved without the use of the science workshop. The science workshop therefore needs to be made available where it is completely absent and equipped where and when we have incomplete facilities and equipment. It has also become imperative that science workshops be upgraded to keep abreast of new skills, techniques and methodologies for sustainable growth and development of science and technical education in our secondary schools. This is because qualitative science and technology education is essential for every young scientist aiming to make a mark in the field of science and technology.

Keywords: Science workshop, Secondary School, needed reforms.

Introduction

The pivotal place of science and technology education in our national development cannot be over-emphasized. The fact that qualitative science and technology education is the vehicle for any societal development is no longer disputable. The strength of a country in

the area of science and technology is determined greatly by the level of development of its scientist and technologist. The scientist and technologist cannot be over emphasized without a sound qualitative science education which can be achieved by effectively using the workshop.

According to William (2002) science is the intellectual and practical activity that moves a systematic study of the structure of the physical and natural world and their behavior through observation and experiment technology according to the hallmark of science is that it generates theories and laws that must be consistent with observation (NSTA 2007). The assumption above clearly makes achievement of quality science and technology education without adequate use of the workshop a mirage. Any society that strives to catch up with global trends in advancement of science and technology should not overlook the basics of science and technology education-science workshop practice.

In the 21st century where advancement in science and technology has turned the world into a global village therefore it is not out of place to pay attention to the foundation. The need for stakeholders in the secondary school science and technology educational system to recognize the role of science workshop in secondary school the constraints in achieving the goal and then put in place adequate measures to tackle the problem militating against its effective use cannot be over emphasized.

The Concept of Science Workshop

Williams (2002), defines Science as the intellectual and practical activity that involves a study of the structure of the physical and natural world and their behavior through observation and experiment. Daniel (2002) defined workshop as a place where machinery and equipment are developed from the application of scientific knowledge. Science workshop therefore is a facility (room or building) where the use of machineries and equipment are employed in a systematic way in order to study the physical and natural

world. All knowledge and theory in science has originated from practical observation and experimentation. (Onwu, 2004). Most of these practical observations and experimentations take place in the workshop as indicated in the definition of the workshop above.

Basic Science and Technology Curriculum, (2012), stated that the purpose of the workshop training given to the students at the secondary school level are:

1. Introduction into the world of technology towards interest arousal and choice of vocation at the end of secondary school education
2. To enable student understand their natural talent by exploring variables created by the various aspects of workshop practice
3. To encourage good career awareness and understanding the demand of the increasing modernization in technology.
4. Workshop practice also stimulates creativity.

The quality and quantity of practical experience gained by secondary school students during workshop experience is a function of the availability of workshop facilities and of course its good management. Okoro (1991), pointed that for a good quality technological development to be achieved, workshop practice must be given its rightful place in the secondary school curriculum.

The Concept of Secondary School Education

Basic Science and Technology Curriculum, (2012), defined secondary school education as the education individuals receive after primary school. Aguisibo (2003) is of the opinion that secondary education as the name implies is the second level of the three tier system of education in Nigeria. The missionary according to Urama (2008) introduced secondary school in Nigeria and it started in the late 1850s.

Aims of Secondary School Education

According to the Basic Science and Technology Curriculum, (2012), the broad aims of secondary school education are:

1. Preparing students for a useful living in the society.
2. Preparation for higher education.

Secondary school is the connection between the primary and the tertiary levels of education and the professionals in various fields of technology today, all started from the secondary school.

Workshop Based Education

Secondary school is considered the most effective means of bringing about technological change that would ensure accelerated development of scientist technicians, technologist and even engineers. According to Okoro (1991), there is need for qualitative change and learning facilities in schools to enable the formation of the basis for the production of graduates that can perform competitively in their chosen careers. Although our traditional student course evaluation and instructional method seem to have provided a favorable student course evaluation technique, this knowledge does not last beyond the end of the term. There is therefore need to provide a more lasting science teaching and learning experience through workshop practice. This experience according Daniel et al, (2002), makes connection between the science student and the environment more understandable.

Objective of the science workshop can be categorized into three according to Basic Science and Technology Curriculum, (2012)

1. To promote basic technical orientation for further training in technology
2. To provide pre-technological literacy for everyday life
3. To stimulate creativity among student

However, the aim and objective of the establishment of the science workshop seems to be close to being defeated because of the secondary school student seem not to be prepared for useful living within the society

Benefitsof the Effective Use of the Science Workshops

- a. **Helps to bring home ideas that were hitherto vague:** Some scientific ideas even when they have been proven severally by renowned scientist still sound like fairly tales to students. It is therefore the responsibility of the teacher to use whatever means available at his/her disposal to make the facts and theories digestible to the confused students. The simple fact that plants need light for photosynthesis may not make any meaning to a student until he/she sees it demonstrated using potted plants. A student may never understand fully the theory that ammonia has a choking smell until the student is exposed to a raw ammonia. The workshop provides facilities for the two instances given above because the practical experience help students learn to use scientific reasoning techniques to define and solve problems and draw and evaluate conclusion based on qualitative evidence. In the workshop therefore ideas are made real in the young minds of these future scientist and this enables them perform effectively in their chosen careers.
- b. **Encourages drive for science-based careers in higher institution:** During workshop practice, students have opportunities to conduct investigations, engage in scientific reasoning, manipulate equipment, record data, analyze results and discuss their findings (NSTA 2007). This makes them well-groomed in science education and they become more aware of the drive in them in the area of science and technology and

may decide to pursue any career in science and technology without inhibition. In most cases, as a result of these exposures, students are able to determine exactly where they fit in, among the sciencebased subjects in the secondary school, and build a successful career on it.

- c. **Produces globally recognized and award winning scientists and sciencebasedprofessionals:** The qualitative nature of the science education foundation of these students has demystified myths surrounding some scientific theories and this makes the students become very confident of themselves because they are psychologically prepared for the challenges ahead. They mix up professionally with other scientist from more developed countries and most times become award winners for the country.
- d. **Produce better equipped and demonstrational science teachers:** Exposure to workshopexperience at the secondary school level is important because most teachers develop their workshoppractice techniques based on their own secondary school workshop experiences (NSTA, 2007). The content to today's science curriculum are improved version of yesterday's so, these teachers, having undergone sound workshop-based science education will be more willing and ready to pass this knowledge to their students
- e. **Encourages a more cordial relationship between teachers and students:** Onwu (2004) strongly advocated that the workshop method of teaching science is the most effective for the development of the technical skills in students. The workshop method of teaching science is therefore an activity oriented approach in which the teacher takes the students to the workshop, gives them guidelines to the activities to be carried out and moves round observing the students as they carry out the activities on their own. In this way teachers spend more quality time with their students which eventually bring about high degree of familiarity between both parties. Irrespective of these benefits of

the workshop, it has failed over the years in providing the desired qualitative science education in our secondary schools.

Factors that limit the use of the Science Workshop in providing Quality Science and Technology Education

- a. **Student's negative attitude to practical:** Most students are discouraged by myths about some scientific and technical theories while others do not understand the several signs in the workshop. Yet many others exhibit nonchallant attitude toward their practical work because they see it as taking their time. As far as they are concerned, every subject should end in the theory class with little or no contribution from them. They want to just sit down and listen.

- b. **Inadequate provision of workshop equipment:** These are cases where the teacher observes that the required equipment in the workshop is not available; he/she improvises the equipment. These improvised materials may not have been originally made for that purpose. For instance, a teacher may decide to use hand lens in place of microscope because of the unavailability of microscope. If this happens almost all the time, a science student may never recognize a microscope when he/she sees one even as a holder of senior school certificate with a credit in Biology. This situation is real in our society today and is the root cause of poor science practice.

- c. **Absence of qualified workshop technologist:** Most secondary schools lack the presence of qualified workshop technicians/technologist in their workshops. These students make do with the science teachers available who are not trained to operate some of the equipment in the workshop. These science teachers by virtue of that training do not have the technical know-how to handle these equipment which means they lack

the required skill for putting some of the scientific theories and facts into practical knowledge for the students

- d. **Unsafe laboratory practices by some teachers:** Some science teachers are not safety – conscious during practical lessons. They create avoidable accidents, making students see the workshop as a death trap, teachers should also understand potential hazards before any practical; this obviously serves well in minimizing workshop accidents. This way, students do not have the impression that some experiments are time bombs waiting for explosion. (Cheesbrough, 2006).
- e. **Poor funding of government owned secondary schools:** The Nigerian secondary schools have not been receiving the required attention from the government (Federal, State and Local government levels) despite their distinct roles of providing sound educational foundation for any career development. Instead of the government to pay attention to the requirements of the existing schools, they build more ill-equipped ones.
- f. **Complete absence of science workshop in some secondary schools:** Although the government has provided some schools with science workshop; there are those without workshop at all. Science workshop must be an integral part of the science curriculum (Arowolo, 2003).
- g. **Lack of incentives to science teachers:** The nature of the jobs of science teachers in our Nigerian secondary schools are not put into consideration during payment of salaries. The fact that they are not given incentives discourages these teachers from performing optimally. They are tempted to end the science classes with mere tutorials like their non-science counterparts because they are paid the same salaries. There is little or no distinction in their salaries to accommodate the extra hours these science teachers spend in the workshop with their students.
- h. **Poor Implementation of science Curriculum by some school heads:** Some principals do not encourage science teachers to use the workshop effectively either because they

are ignorant of the benefits of the workshop in science education or simple do not care about the quality of science education in their schools. This development is rather unfortunate because the primary assignment of any visionary principal is to ensure that education quality of his / her institution is at its peak during his / her tenure.

- i. **Poor practical lessons preparation / presentation:** Science teachers should come to the workshop with a plan for the use of their time and some understanding of what he / she are about to do. Some teachers also lack the required skill because they are also product of secondary schools with poorly equipped or poorly used workshops. Their poor background makes it almost impossible to pass any sound practical knowledge to the students who may become more confused, than they were before the practical. (Aguisibo, 1998) believe the governments are building more ill- equipped secondary schools with of course ill- functional laboratories. The most discouraging part is the fact that most times the so called well equipped secondary schools only exist on the pages of newspaper or on television. The reverse becomes the case when you visit some of these secondary schools. Some secondary school heads that have the desire to improve the quality of science education in their schools are given insufficient grants to run the schools. If the grants is not sufficient where does the school get funds for the provision of some not too expensive consumables needed for practical or even improvise in the absence of the proper materials / equipments?.
- j. **Bastardization of secondary school science curriculum by some private secondary school proprietors.** Some private secondary school proprietors have reduced the quality of science education to near zero level. In a bid to economize funds, the proprietors employ unqualified teachers who are unable to do any form of practical for the students. Some of them only hire workshop equipment during the senior school certificate examination for the practical although some of the practical are mere make

believes; they really do not take place. Some of the make believe practical are done in environment unsuitable for use as a workshop. Imagine a situation where the teachers' office become emergency workshop and then equipment are quickly dismantled immediately after the exercise. With all these factors militating against the effective use of the workshop, the workshop is highly constrained from carrying out its major role of improving the quality of science education in Nigerian secondary schools.

Conclusion

I strongly believe that if the factors responsible for the poor utilization of the workshop in providing qualitative science and technical education are taken care of and the workshop becomes efficient in carrying out its responsibly in this regard, we will be on our way to achieving qualitative science and technical education.

Recommendations and Needed Reforms

Based on the various limitations of the workshop in providing qualitative science education, the following recommendations are therefore made on the ways the workshop can be used to provide qualitative science education in Nigerian secondary schools:

1. Employment of qualified science workshop technologists: qualified science workshop technology should be employed in the secondary schools by the government to manage the workshop and teach the students the practical aspect of any topic that should involves workshop sessions. However, the workshop technicians/technologist may be required to undergo a form of training (like post graduated diploma in education) to enable them fit in better and be more focused in achieving set goals.
2. The science teachers should be made to undergo training in workshop practice techniques and management to enable them performs better in the workshop.

3. Provision of well equipped science workshops in all Nigerian secondary schools: It is not enough to have science workshops in most secondary schools, we should have them in all secondary schools and they should be well equipped. Adequate attention should also be given to those in the rural areas, the private schools ought to be monitored too to ensure their compliance in workshop acquisition and management.
4. Re – Orientation of students on workshop based science and technology education: The student should be made to understand the importance of the workshop in science and technology education and they should know that they cannot have a clear understanding of the scientific theories they are taught without the use of the workshop for the practical involved. They must know that the workshop is the heart of science and technology education. They must also be made to participate during practical instead of being spectators. In addition to the above recommendation, the government should increase its level of commitment to the science teachers, ensure the administrators are using their grants judiciously and that science teachers are sent on training to update them with the necessary experience and exposure for better performance. These reforms are necessary to achieve a maximum utilization of the workshop.

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